

Perspective for Molecular Neurodegeneration

Next-generation hiPSC-based models to decipher the contribution of human astrocytes to Alzheimer's disease and potential targeting therapeutics

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Astrocytes constitute a large part of the brain cell mass and play essential functions in the central nervous system (CNS). They maintain brain homeostasis, provide trophic and metabolic support to neurons, regulate synapse formation, neurotransmission and calcium homeostasis, and control immune response and blood flow. In Alzheimer's disease (AD), astrocytes undergo profound molecular, morphological and functional alterations that arise at early stages and exacerbate as disease evolves, indicating that astrocytes transition from homeostatic to dysfunctional disease-associated states and pointing to these cells as critical contributors to AD progression. Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) support this idea as many putative genes increasing the risk for developing late-onset AD (LOAD) are primarily expressed in glial cells, among which the major AD risk genes *APOE*, *CLU* and *FERMT2* are predominantly expressed in astrocytes. While our current knowledge of astrocyte contribution to AD is mainly coming from studies in mouse models, critical species-specific differences highlight the importance of studying astrocyte (dys)function in human-based systems. The ability to generate human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) from patients and differentiate them into astrocytes is providing exciting opportunities to explore their functions in AD. We summarize below recent studies in 2D and 3D cultures, co-culture systems and organoids giving essential clues on the impact of human astrocytes on AD, and propose potential astrocyte-targeting therapeutics.

Earlier studies in 2D models revealed that healthy hiPSC-derived astrocytes play important roles in APP processing, secrete β -amyloid ($A\beta$) (1), and therefore have the potential to contribute to $A\beta$ accumulation in AD brains. Astrocytes derived from AD patients carrying the *PSEN1* $\Delta E9$ mutation display AD hallmarks including increased $A\beta$ and reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, altered inflammatory responses and dysregulated calcium homeostasis compared to isogenic control astrocytes (2). When co-cultured with *PSEN1* mutant astrocytes in a 3D system, isogenic control neurons also display alterations in calcium signaling (2), which highlights a major impact of human astrocytes on human neuron physiology and functionality. Interestingly, activation of NF-E2-related factor 2 (NRF2), key regulator of antioxidant defense pathways, reduces $A\beta$ secretion and modulates cytokine release and oxidative stress in *PSEN1* mutant astrocytes (3), suggesting that targeting NRF2 in AD astrocytes could be a potential therapeutic strategy.

Astrocytes are the major cell type expressing and producing the protein apolipoprotein E (apoE) in the brain, although microglia, particularly in an activated state, also produce apoE. ApoE facilitates the transport of lipids and cholesterol to neurons, microglia and oligodendrocytes, and binds to $A\beta$ plaques. The *APOE* gene has three polymorphic alleles ($\epsilon 2$, $\epsilon 3$ and $\epsilon 4$), being *APOE4* the one conferring the greatest risk for LOAD with an earlier age of disease onset in a gene dose-dependent manner. Recent studies have started to elucidate how *APOE* affects human astrocyte functions in the context of AD. hiPSC-derived astrocytes carrying the *APOE4* variant produce and secrete less apoE protein compared to *APOE3* astrocytes, are less efficient at clearing the extracellular $A\beta$, and show impaired lipid/cholesterol metabolism (4,5). Astrocytes are one of the major cell types producing cholesterol, and increased cholesterol biosynthesis has also been found in organoids from individuals carrying Tau mutations (6), suggesting that perturbed cholesterol metabolism is a common pathway and early event in the etiology of AD. Besides, *APOE4* astrocytes show increased inflammatory responses compared to *APOE3* astrocytes (5). A recent study describes an exacerbated proinflammatory state on *APOE4* astrocytes associated with Transgelin

3 (TAGLN3) downregulation and NF- κ B activation (7). Interestingly, this state can be pharmacologically reverted by TAGLN3 supplementation, highlighting TAGLN3 as a target to modulate inflammation in *APOE4* astrocytes. Importantly, imbalances at cell-autonomous level also affect astrocyte-neuron communication. When co-cultured with neurons, *APOE4* astrocytes provide less support for neuronal survival and synaptogenesis (8). Moreover, in organoids composed by either *APOE3* or *APOE4* neurons and astrocytes there is increased *APOE4*-dependent synapse loss, neurodegeneration and Tau pathology (4,9).

Astrocyte-microglia crosstalk also has an impact on AD-associated inflammatory processes. In tri-culture systems with healthy hiPSC-derived astrocytes, neurons and microglia, the complement protein C3, which is elevated in brains of AD patients and involved in neurodegeneration, increases under inflammatory conditions due to astrocyte-microglia reciprocal signaling that induces them to overproduce C3. Astrocytic production of C3 induced by microglia, as well as microglial production of C3 re-induced by astrocytes are further enhanced in AD tri-cultures derived from hiPSCs harboring the *APP^{SWE}* mutation (10). Another 3D tri-culture AD model that develops A β pathology and Tau accumulation shows that astrocyte-secreted interleukin-3 (IL-3) reprograms microglia at molecular, morphological and functional levels. Reprogrammed microglia acquire an acute immune response, increased motility and enhanced capacity to cluster and clear A β and Tau aggregates restricting AD pathology (11). Astrocytes secrete other inflammatory factors and molecules potentially involved in their crosstalk with microglia, neurons and other brain cells. hiPSC-based *in vitro* systems are best suited for modeling the inflammatory axis between these cells, dissecting the role of astrocytes in complex AD cellular environments and their impact on neurodegeneration in AD. Moreover, these models constitute a powerful approach for identifying key compounds and main molecular players enabling the development of astrocyte targeting therapeutic strategies.

In summary, human astrocytes get dysfunctional at early stages of AD and aggravate the pathology affecting major processes including A β production/clearance, cholesterol/lipid metabolism, oxidative stress and calcium dynamics. Moreover, in AD, human astrocytes lose their homeostatic functions providing less support to synapses and neurons, while closely interacting with microglia, being key mediators of neuroinflammation. Novel therapeutic strategies targeting astrocytes should aim at enhancing their neurotrophic/neuroprotective properties, modulating their immune responses, and reversing their lipid/cholesterol metabolic alterations, oxidative stress and calcium dysfunction. Next-generation hiPSC-based approaches should include as well *in vivo* analyses of human astrocytes transplanted in chimeric AD mice (12). Chimeras offer a unique opportunity to analyze human astrocyte dysfunction in the live AD brain and how it contributes to AD progression. Combination of *in vitro* and *in vivo* models with CRISPR-Cas9 editing to allow targeting specific AD risk genes or variants in human astrocytes, transcriptomics and high-resolution imaging will be critical for further exploring the role of human astrocytes in AD, and it will open new avenues enabling the development of astrocyte-specific targeting therapeutics to prevent, slow down and even cure AD.

List of abbreviations:

CNS: Central nervous system; AD: Alzheimer' s disease; GWAS: Genome-wide association studies; LOAD: late-onset AD; hiPSC: human induced pluripotent stem cells; A β : β -amyloid; ROS: reactive oxygen species; apoE: apolipoprotein E; TAGLN3: Transgelin 3; IL-3: interleukin-3.

Declarations:**Ethics approval and consent to participate**

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Competing interests

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Authors' contributions

JTCW and AMA wrote the first version of the manuscript and revised it. JTCW and AMA prepared the figure. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Figure 1. Human astrocytes get dysfunctional at early stages of AD and exacerbate the pathology affecting major AD processes. Combination of hiPSC-based in vitro and in vivo models with gene editing, transcriptomics and high-resolution imaging will allow in depth analyses of human astrocytes in AD and enable the development of astrocyte targeting therapeutics.